

EFFECT OF STRESS RATIO ON DELAMINATION GROWTH BEHAVIOR IN UNIDIRECTIONAL CARBON/EPOXY UNDER MODE I FATIGUE LOADING

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SUMMARY

Effect of stress ratio on the Mode I delamination growth behaviour of composite structures under fatigue loading has been investigated. Mode I cyclic delamination growth tests were conducted on unidirectional M30SC/DT120 laminates under stress ratios of 0.15, 0.35 and 0.5. The fracture surfaces have shown different topography under different cyclic stress ratios.

Key Words: Delamination growth, Stress Ratio, Strain Energy Release Rate, Double cantilever Beam, Mode I, SEM

1. INTRODUCTION

The presence of delaminations and their effect on structural performance is the most common threat to the use of composite materials in primary structural applications. Composite structures may contain delaminations due to bad layup and defects during manufacturing and assembling processes. Delaminations may also be developed in a composite structure due to in service impacts, static overloads and fatigue. Cyclic loading can cause delaminations to grow in size, which results in redistribution of structural loads and can cause more delaminations in other locations of the structure and lead towards structural failure[1].

Understanding delamination growth behavior under cyclic loading is necessary for damage tolerant design and reliability assessment of composite structures. However, due to the complex nature of the problem, it is not an easy task. Several researchers [2-12] have studied delamination growth behavior under cyclic loading. The cyclic stress ratio (R-ratio), which is the ratio of minimum cyclic stress to maximum cyclic stress, is known to influence delamination growth behavior [13-16]. Hojo et al [13]. developed a relation between delamination rate and equivalent Stress Intensity Factor (SIF), which is an empirical function of SIF range and R-ratio. Tanaka and Tanaka [14] incorporated the effects of R-ratio by empirically deriving a relation for the exponent of the Paris power law in terms of R-ratio. Schon [15] related Paris law exponent to R-ratio, Strain Energy Release Rate (SERR) range at threshold, critical SERR, and the corresponding delamination rates. Andersons et. al [16] extended the empirical model of Hojo et al [13] for R-ratio effect,

however the equivalent SIF in this case is a function of damage accumulation ahead of delamination front.

From the review of the previous studies for R-ratio effect on delamination growth, it is evident that these past efforts have focused on the development of empirical models without the development of a mechanistic understanding of the effect. In order to produce a generic delamination growth model, a mechanistic approach is needed.

The main goal of the present study was to explain the mechanisms responsible for the R-ratio effect on delamination growth behavior under Mode I cyclic load. The secondary goal was the validation of a recently proposed controlling fracture mechanics parameter [17] for delamination growth. Delamination growth tests have been carried out under Mode I cyclic loadings on unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminates. Fracture surfaces were examined using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM).

First a brief introduction to the adopted fracture mechanics parameter used in this study will be presented. Subsequently the experimental study into the R-ratio effects on Mode I delamination growth in carbon epoxy laminates will be presented.

2. CONTROLLING FRACTURE MECHANICS PARAMETER FOR DELAMINATION GROWTH

There are several approaches toward controlling fracture mechanics parameter for delamination growth. Some researchers [13, 16] have used SIF range as fracture mechanics parameter for delamination growth. However, due to complex stress field at delamination front, its evaluation is difficult for orthotropic composite laminates making it inconvenient for such materials. Using strain energy release rate as controlling fracture mechanics parameter is an effective alternative for delamination growth analysis and widely adopted by researchers [2, 5, 6, 12, 18]. The problem with the SERR approach is the lack of consensus on the formulation of the strain energy release rate used to characterize fatigue delamination growth.

Two commonly adopted formulations for SERR used to characterize fatigue delamination growth are the use of maximum energy release rate G_{\max} [5] and the energy release rate range $\Delta G = G_{\max} - G_{\min}$ [8, 9, 18]. The prevalent use of G_{\max} stems from its importance in assessing the limits for static delamination propagation. For delamination growth related to cyclic loading, however, this parameter fails to consider the effect of the minimum energy release rate, G_{\min} , related to the minimum load in the applied load cycle. Use of energy release rate range, $\Delta G = G_{\max} - G_{\min}$, attempts to remove this shortcoming in a manner analogous to the SIF range, ΔK , used for crack growth in metals. The simple arithmetic difference in maximum and minimum SERRs, however, fails to adhere to the rules of superposition for SERR, thus violating the similitude principle central to linear elastic fracture mechanics.

To overcome the previous shortcomings of existing SERR formulations, Rans [17] proposed a new formulation based on the rules of superposition for SERR and in keeping with the principle of similitude used for characterizing crack growth in metals. Rans

demonstrated that in fact the strain energy release rate range should be formulated as: $\Delta G = G_{eff} = \left(\sqrt{G_{max}} - \sqrt{G_{min}} \right)^2$. In the present paper this approach is adopted and the results are compared with the previous approach of ΔG .

3. EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

Based on the proposed SERR formulation for delamination characterization proposed by Rans, an experimental investigation of R-ratio effects on Mode I fatigue delamination growth was performed. Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) specimens, prepared according to ASTM 5528 [19], were used for the delamination growth experiment.

The specimens were made of carbon/epoxy prepreg, M30SC/DT120, supplied by Delta-Tech S.p.A. Properties of the prepreg are given in table 1. A laminate panel was made by stacking 28 plies of the prepreg in a unidirectional layup. During layup, a Teflon insert of 12.7 μm thickness and 40 mm width was placed at the edge of the panel between the 14th and 15th ply to act as a starter delamination. The panel was cured in an autoclave at a pressure of 6 bars and temperature of 120°C for 90 minutes, according to the material supplier recommendations.

Table 1 Properties of M30SC/DT120 prepreg

Longitudinal elastic modulus (Gpa)	150
Transverse elastic modulus (Gpa)	7
In plane Poison ratio	0.29
Fiber weight fraction (%)	66

After curing, the panel was ultrasonically scanned for imperfections. DCB specimens of 20 mm width were cut out from the defect free portions of the panel. Aluminum tabs were bonded to specimens in order to facilitate its fastening to the hinges of the DCB test fixture. Geometry of a DCB specimen with hinges attached is shown in figure 1.

3.1 Fatigue Test Procedure

Mode I cyclic delamination growth tests were performed in a 10 kN MTS machine with a load cell of 10 kN capacity. Tests were conducted at room temperature under cyclic frequency of 3 Hz. All the tests were performed under displacement controlled conditions. Maximum and minimum cyclic displacements were evaluated by a static fracture test prior to fatigue test. Maximum cyclic load at the start of fatigue test was taken to be equal to 80 % of the load at static fracture. Corresponding maximum displacement was evaluated by statically loading the specimen. Minimum cyclic load at the start of fatigue test was evaluated by multiplying the R-ratio with the maximum load. The corresponding minimum displacement was evaluated by statically loading the specimen to minimum load. Maximum and minimum displacements were fixed during fatigue test. The above procedure was repe-

Figure 1 DCB specimen with aluminum tabs and hinge setup

ated for every fatigue test at different R-ratio and different initial delamination lengths of the specimens.

A total of 4 DCB specimens were fatigue tested. The DCB 1, 3 and 4 were tested under R-ratio of 0.15. Two different initial delamination lengths of the DCB 4 were used for testing under R-ratio of 0.15. Two fatigue tests were performed on DCB 2 under R-ratio of 0.35 at two different initial delamination lengths. Fatigue delamination tests under R-ratio of 0.5 were performed on DCB 2 at three different initial delamination lengths. Details of initial delamination lengths of the specimens for the fatigue tests under different R-ratios are given in table 2.

Table 2 Initial delamination lengths of DCB specimens under various stress ratios of Mode I cyclic tests

R-Ratio	Initial delamination length (mm)			
	DCB 1	DCB 2	DCB 3	DCB 4
0.15	53	---	46	29 , 39
0.35	---	20,32	---	---
0.5	---	27,51,67	---	---

Delamination growth was monitored by a digital camera and computer system. The Lab VIEW 8.6 software package was programmed for fatigue tests and interfaced to the MTS

machine for automatic capturing of images of the specimen after every 1000 cycles. Delamination was monitored from the edge of the specimen. A thin layer of water based correction fluid was applied to the edge to enhance delamination visibility and marked paper scale was attached for delamination length measurements.

3.2. Energy Release rate and Delamination Growth rate Calculations

Energy release rates were calculated by the compliance method [20]. The compliances of the DCB specimen were calculated during fatigue test by equation 1

$$C = \frac{\delta}{F} \quad (1)$$

Where δ is displacement and F is force at Nth cycle

Delamination lengths at corresponding fatigue cycles were evaluated from the corresponding images taken by camera. A power law relation was established between compliance and delamination length as given by equation

$$C = ma^n \quad (2)$$

Where ' a ' is delamination length and m and n are power law parameters. The compliance-delamination length relation was established separately for every fatigue test for each DCB specimen. Energy release rates were calculated according to the relation [20].

$$G = \frac{F^2}{2w} \frac{dC}{da} \quad (3)$$

Where F is the resultant force due to applied displacement at Nth cycle and w is the width of the specimen.

Delamination growth rates were calculated by ASTM E 647 [21] data reduction technique and plotted against corresponding effective strain energy release rates given by G_{eff} and ΔG as shown in figures 2a and 2b respectively.

3.3. SEM Investigations

Delamination growth experiments under Mode I fatigue loading were performed for investigation of R-ratio effect on delamination growth rate. After completing the tests, the specimens were completely peeled to expose the fracture surfaces for SEM investigations. The two pieces were further divided into the areas according to specific R-ratios. SEM

images of fracture surfaces at these locations were taken at magnification of 4000x to find the differences between the fracture surface profiles under different R-ratios. SEM investigations of the fracture surfaces under cyclic R-ratios of 0.15, 0.35 and 0.5 are revealed by SEM images shown in figures 4a, 4b and 4c. Direction of delamination growth is shown by black arrows in the figures.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Comparison of SERR Formulations

The effect of R-ratio on delamination growth rate in Mode I cyclic loading was investigated experimentally. The results under R-ratios of 0.15, 0.35 and 0.5 were compared for SERR formulations G_{eff} and ΔG and plotted in Figure 2a and 2b respectively. At first glance, it appears that using ΔG as a fracture mechanics parameter reduces scatter and provides a more generic description of delamination growth behavior at the R-ratios studied. However, upon closer inspection of the data for the individual R-ratios, it was observed that scatter was reduced when using G_{eff} . This is illustrated by the R-squared values for the different data sets given in Table 3.

The reason for the higher degree of scatter in the data when using ΔG is the violation of similitude when using this parameter, as described by Rans [17]. Within this study, multiple tests were performed for each R-ratio using differing DCB opening displacement. As a result, multiple data points are obtained for each ΔG value with differing combinations of delamination length and DCB opening displacement. If similitude is preserved in the governing fracture mechanics parameter, it is expected that the delamination growth behavior will be the same for a given value of that fracture mechanics

Figure 2 Delamination rates vs. SERR (a) G_{eff} (b) ΔG

Table 3 R-squared values for SERR formulations under R-ratio of 0.15, 0.35 and 0.

R-ratio		0,15	0,35	0,5
R-squared value	$G_{eff} = (\sqrt{G_{max}} - \sqrt{G_{min}})^2$	0,81	0,74	0,83
	$\Delta G = G_{max} - G_{min}$	0,78	0,38	0,67

parameter. This is not the case for ΔG as shown in Figure 3a,. Two separate and distinct trend lines become visible for the two delamination growth tests conducted with differing DCB opening displacements. When G_{eff} is applied as a fracture mechanics parameter, however, the two data sets collapse onto one trend line as similitude is preserved with this fracture mechanics parameter (see Figure 3b).

4.2. SERR Formulations and R-ratio Effect

Ideally there should be no R-ratio effect on crack growth in fatigue under linear elastic fracture mechanics theory. In fact, the identified mechanisms for R-ratio effects observed for crack growth in metals are related to violations to the assumptions within linear elastic fracture mechanics such as crack tip plasticity. An effect of R-ratio on delamination growth was observed using proposed formulation of G_{eff} , which is based on linear elastic fracture mechanics. This R-ratio effect, as in crack growth in metals, is likely the result of a non-linear mechanism such as crack closure due to asperities (roughness induced crack closure), presence of broken fibers and fiber pullouts at delamination front.

Figure 3 Variation in the effect of opening displacement on delamination growth behavior under R-ratio of 0.35 with respect to SERR formulations (a) G_{eff} (b) ΔG

The R-ratio effect was unclear and data points at different R-ratios were mixed randomly for the data obtained in this study when ΔG formulation was used as shown in figure 2b, making analysis of R-ratio effect difficult. The difference between delamination behaviors under different R-ratios is clear and understandable in case of G_{eff} and it may be argued that this formulation is a better alternative as compared to ΔG formulation for the R-ratio effect assessment due to nonlinear mechanisms.

4.3. SEM investigations of fracture surfaces

Results of the investigations of fracture surfaces for R-ratio effect have shown some indications of difference in the surface profiles under R-ratios of 0.15, 0.35 and 0.5. Fracture surface resulted under R-ratio of 0.15 shown in 4a, has less roughness than other two surfaces under 0.35 and 0.5. The surface under R-ratio of 0.35 may be regarded as having intermediate roughness compared to others with highest roughness under R-ratio of 0.5 as shown in figures 4b and 4c.

It may be postulated here that all the fracture surfaces evolved with the same roughness profile under different R-ratios, immediately after fracture. However for lower R-ratios, the surface became smoother due to repeated compression of the fracture surface asperities at the low end of the fatigue cycle, thus generating a closure effect and terminating the roughness as the fatigue test was progressed.

For fully understanding R-ratio effect, the measure of the degree of roughness like the heights of asperities generated due to delamination fracture and the effect of contacting lengths of the opposite surfaces under different R-ratios however, needs further investigations

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 4 SEM images of fracture surfaces at magnification 4K under cyclic R-ratio (a) 0.15 (b) 0.35 and (c) 0.5

5. CONCLUSIONS

Delamination growth tests under Mode I cyclic loading were conducted on unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminates, made of M30SC/DT120 prepreg, under R-ratio s of 0.15, 0.35 and 0.5. Following conclusions were made from the results

1. For the same R-ratios, the scatter of delamination growth data is significantly reduced by using proposed formulation of G_{eff} as a result of this parameter adhering to the similitude principle.
2. For different R-ratios, plots of delamination growth rate vs. G_{eff} show distinct trends for each R-ratio. The trends vary in an understandable and differentiable manner from lower to higher R-ratios, making further study of R-ratio effects possible.
3. Delamination rate vs. ΔG plots under various R-ratio mixes all the data points randomly, making R-ratio effect difficult to observe.
4. The fracture surface profiles for different R-ratios show a difference in surface topography that may indicate a variation in roughness induced crack closure. Further investigation is needed to explore this.

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